

PROPERTY EVALUATION OF CFRP SANDWICH PANEL UNDER CRYOGENIC TEMPERATURE

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the demand of large-size primary mirrors for infrared telescopes is increasing to perform high-sensitivity observation in the space. Also, infrared telescope systems operated under cryogenic temperature are needed for the observation of mid-to-far wavelength infrared rays. In addition, the weight of space satellite is severely restricted by the capability of launching rocket. Under these backgrounds, structural material of primary mirror for the infrared telescope demands superior characteristics such as lightweight, high stiffness, stable mechanical properties at low temperature and high surface accuracy¹⁾.

Therefore, sandwich structures with carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) for skin material are one of attractive candidates because they have above-mentioned advantageous characteristics as well as low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE).

In the present study, we focus on the development of primary mirror made of sandwich panel with CFRP skin. For cores, foamed core and honeycomb core were selected.

Several characteristics of sandwiches, such as flexural rigidity, flatwise tensile strength and surface accuracy were evaluated. The flatwise tension test was performed at temperatures of RT (room temperature), -150°C (representative of a satellite in orbit) and -60°C (intermediate temperature), to evaluate the effect of temperature on the mechanical behavior of the sandwiches.

2 Materials and experimental procedure

2.1 Materials

Raw material for the skin was a unidirectional prepreg (TORAYCA T700S) which was stacked so as to make quasi-isotropic plate, [0/±60]_s.

We selected two kinds of core materials, that is, Al honeycomb core (AL3/8-5052-001) and foamed core (ROHACELL WF51) with two core thicknesses of 10 and 20mm. A two-step method was used for the Al honeycomb core sandwich (CFRP/Honeycomb), where the CFRP skin panel was first cured followed by adhesion to core using a sheet-type adhesive (AF163-2K 0.6wt). In the case of foamed core sandwich (CFRP/Foam), a co-cure method was used, that is, the cure of the skin panel and the adhesion to the core is done simultaneously.

In the present study, a handy autoclave was used for the molding.

2.2 four-point bending test

The four-point bending test was performed in accordance with the ASTM standard C393-00²⁾; Fig.1 shows the test configuration. The span, L , and specimen width, b , was fixed to 360mm 60mm, respectively. During the test, the crosshead speed was kept constant, 1.5 mm/min. The radius of supporting and loading nose was 5 mm. A dial gage was used to measure the deflection.

The flexural rigidity EI_{exp} was calculated by equation (1);

$$EI_{\text{exp}} = \frac{23PL^3}{1296\delta_{\text{exp}}} \quad (1)$$

where P is the applied load and L is the span, and δ_{exp} is the deflection³⁾.

Fig. 1 Test configuration of four-point bending test.

2.3 Flatwise tension test

The flatwise tension test was performed in accordance with the ASTM standard C297⁴⁾. The specimen size was 80×80mm, and the skin surface was bonded to a loading block with an epoxy-type adhesive (Araldite AR-S30). The tensile tests were performed at test temperatures of RT, -60°C and -150°C while the crosshead speed was kept constant, 0.5 mm/min. The flatwise tension test configuration was shown Fig. 2.

The flatwise tensile strength (F^{ftu}) was determined by equation (2);

$$F^{ftu} = \frac{P_{max}}{A} \quad (2)$$

where P_{max} is the maximum load and A is the bonded area.

Fig. 2 Test configuration of flatwise tension test.

2.4 3D profile measurement

The 3D profile was measured using a 3D profilometer (LK-GD500 KS-1100). An arbitrary range of 20×20mm was chosen and this area was scanned for 3D profile measurement. The scanning

speed was 7500μm/s in the 90° direction, and the scanning interval in the 0° direction was 10μm, where 0° is the fiber direction of the skin surface, and 90° shows transverse direction. The surface accuracy was evaluated in terms of RMS (Root Mean Square) value. Schematic view of 3D profilometer was shown Fig. 3.

Fig.3 Schematic view of 3D profilometer.

3 Results and discussion

Figure 4 shows the relation between weight per unit area and flexural rigidity of both sandwiches. These data are experimental values at the span 360mm, and t_c is the thickness of the core materials. Concerning the weight per unit area, CFRP/Foam was lighter than CFRP/Honeycomb at the core thickness of 10mm, whereas the weight of the two sandwiches became almost the same when the core became thicker, 20mm. The scan be understood as follows. As described in Section 2.1, CFRP/Honeycomb was made by skin, core, and adhesive film to bond the core to the skin. In case of CFRP/Foam, only skin and core were used. The apparent density of Al honeycomb is lower than ROHACELL foam. Then, when t_c is small, CFRP/Honeycomb is heavier and with increasing the core thickness, CFRP/Honeycomb is getting relatively lighter.

Now, let's discuss the trend of rigidity. According to sandwich beam theory, the flexural rigidity is proportional to the square of core thickness. The CFRP/Honeycomb could approximately realize it (see Fig.4). On the other hand, the flexural rigidity of CFRP/Foam deviated from the theory, that is, x.x time's flexural rigidity

against double core thickness. This undesirable effect might be caused by either shear deformation due to low shearing modulus of foam core or local dent of core by the loading nose.

Finally, CFRP/Honeycomb was shown to be a lightweight and high stiffness material.

Fig. 4 Weight per unit area versus flexural rigidity.

Figure 5 shows the flatwise tensile strength at room temperature, -60°C, and -150°C. In all cases the F^{ftu} value of CFRP/Honeycomb was higher than that of CFRP/Foam, which suggested that the structural stability of CFRP/Honeycomb was high.

Figures 6 and 7 show the fracture pattern of all kinds of sandwiches subjected to flatwise tension. As shown in Figs.6 and 7, both types of sandwiches showed core failure at any temperature.

As the temperature decreased, the F^{ftu} of CFRP/Honeycomb slightly increased, as shown in Fig.5. It is probably due to the fact that aluminum doesn't show brittleness even at low temperature, and that tensile strength increases. In contrast, F^{ftu} of CFRP/Foam slightly decreased as the temperature decreased, because of ROHACELL exhibiting brittle behavior at low temperature.

Thus, CFRP/Honeycomb seemed more effective than CFRP/Foam under cryogenic temperature.

Fig. 5 Flatwise tensile strength at low temperature.

(a)RT

(b)-60°C

(c)-150°C

Fig. 6 Fracture pattern of CFRP/Honeycomb.

Fig. 7 Fracture pattern of CFRP/Foam.

Figure 8 shows the surface profiles of both sandwiches. Periodical dimples were observed on the skin surface of CFRP/Honeycomb whereas global warpage was observed in the case of CFRP/Foam (Figure 8(a) (b)). The formation of dimple was probably due to the combination of the difference in CTE between skin and core, and hexagonal space of honeycomb structure. The warpage was most likely generated by the low stiffness of the ROHACELL core and small-angle misalignment of prepreg sheets during fabrication of CFRP skin panel.

(a) CFRP/Honeycomb

(b) CFRP/Foam

Fig. 8 Surface profile measurement.

Figure 9 shows the RMS (root mean square) values of surface roughness. In both cases, the RMS values exceeded the design requirement ($<20\mu\text{m}$). It is necessary to carry out careful consideration against these deformations for improving the surface accuracy and the RMS values.

Fig. 9 RMS value of surface roughness.

4 Conclusions

- The weight of CFRP/Honeycomb was smaller than that of CFRP/Foam in the same flexural rigidity, and CFRP/Honeycomb was shown the material that was a lightweight and high stiffness.
- The F^{tu} of CFRP/Honeycomb was higher than that of CFRP/Foam.
- As the temperature decreased, F^{tu} increased for CFRP/Honeycomb, whereas it decreased for CFRP/Foam.

- Periodical dimples were observed on the skin surface of CFRP/Honeycomb whereas global warpage was observed in the case of CFRP/Foam.
- A CFRP/Honeycomb sandwich may become a candidate material, although the area of the present survey was rather limited.

References

- 1) Next-generation infrared astronomical satellite Working Group, "SPICA Mission Proposal ver.2," 2008, pp.11-13,215-220.
- 2) ASTM C393-00 Standard Test Method for Flexural Properties of Sandwich Constructions.
- 3) H. Fukuda and O. Il Byon, "Introduction to Composite Materials," Kokon-Shoin, 1989, pp.46, 80, and 98.
- 4) ASTM C297/C297M-04 Standard Test Method for Flatwise Tensile Strength of Sandwich Constructions.